

An assessment of effectiveness of marketing of financial services

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Abstract

Objective: Effectiveness of marketing of financial services was assessed through a cross-sectional study using a survey questionnaire.

Materials and Methods: Descriptive hypotheses were set and studied based on primary data collected via a survey questionnaire which was administered to 110 individual and corporate investors from Pune who were amongst the top client of investments and financial services firms. The average effectiveness rating of the 110 respondents was compared with point-value 3 of the scale indicating an “effectiveness” rating and was tested for statistical significance @95% confidence level.

Results: Average effectiveness rating by the 110 respondents to the 10 financial services was 3.20 on a maximum scale of 4.

Conclusion: There was wide agreement that the financial services are marketed quite well. This is an encouraging sign for the Indian capital markets.

Keywords: Financial Services, Financial Services Marketing, Investors, Effectiveness

Introduction

Financial service marketing is a method employed by marketing professionals dealing with financial services to bring in new customers and try and retain old ones.

Miremedi and Sadeh (2012), have emphasized the importance of costly communication and promotion tools to market financial services. As there is stiff competition in these fields the marketers also have to deal with the following issues: customer changing behavior; difficulty in attracting college students; non-English speaking customers etc.

To improve the profitability of the marketing instruments the marketing manager has to give importance to the following: understanding the customer’s attitude and beliefs; adequate marketing information; integrated marketing organization; operational efficiency and strategic orientation (Kotler, 1997).

The question remains what criteria should be used to assess the effectiveness of the marketing strategy for financial instruments and they are enumerated as follows: identifiable time horizon; national or international market opportunities; the selected strategy should be consistent with the analysis of the financial service strengths and weaknesses; the levels of risk should be commensurate with the level of profits or goals (Meidan, 1988).

The need to assess effectiveness in this competitive industry is that today; due to increasing liberalization of the financial services market the buyers have an upper hand as compared to the sellers (Appiah-Adu et al, 2001)

Therefore to assess the effectiveness of marketing on financial services, a survey questionnaire was administered to 110 individual and corporate investors from Pune who were amongst the top client of investments and financial services firms.

Literature Review

A study by Miremadi and Sadeh (2012) found that personal selling is statistically significant for the variable-education. Promotion and advertising help to remind people about investing in financial instruments. The study by Zehrihun and Shekhar (2011), prompted that 78.5 % financial performance variation; 86.8% competitive variation; 90.3% consumer behavior variation; 89.3 % direct customer variation, 87.5% innovation variation is affected by marketing effectiveness and efficiency. In short, the financial company's performance is influenced by effective marketing.

A study done in Nigeria's First bank had the following results on the assessment of effects on banking financial services: sixty-two percent of respondents agreed that bank had an increased turnover and better performance due to heavily investing in into marketing as it has a separate marketing department (80%) and seventy-eight percent agreed that it was affordable to the customers that the financial and that it carried out a detailed survey of its customers profile before launching a new product. The bank had a separate marketing budget and uses modern information technology (Akeem, 2014).

Studies evaluating the effectiveness of marketing of financial services are not seen much. Marketing is required for services as much as it is required for goods. Hence this study attempts an evaluation of the effectiveness of marketing of financial services.

Methodology

1. A survey questionnaire was administered to 110 individual and corporate investors from Pune who were amongst the top client of investments and financial services firms.
2. The selection of the 110 investors was based on the judgment of the writer of getting an adequate response in a reasonable time. Convenience sampling was used. However, it was ensured that the respondent has a minimum of five years of investing experience.
3. The survey questionnaire had a list of 10 popular financial services.

The 10 popular financial services selected were as under:

- a. Banking
- b. Wealth Management
- c. Professional advisory
- d. Mutual Funds
- e. Insurance
- f. Treasury/ Debt instruments
- g. Stock Market
- h. Tax and Audit Consultancy
- i. Portfolio Management
- j. Funding services

4. Respondents were asked to rate the effectiveness of marketing of the 10 financial services on a Likert-scale of 0-4: 0- Can't say, 1-Not effective, 2-Little bit effective, 3-Quite effective, 4-Highly effective.

5. The average effectiveness rating of the 110 respondents was compared with point-value 3 of the scale indicating an "effectiveness" rating and was tested for statistical significance @95% confidence level.

Statement of Hypotheses:

Ho1: The marketing of financial services is not effective

Ha1: The marketing of financial services is effective

The survey instrument returned a Cronbach's alpha of 0.879 that is better than 0.70 (the standard) and hence was considered as reliable.

Results

Descriptive analysis:

Table 1: Description of the Respondents

Category of investor		No of Respondents(N=110)
1	Individual	51
2	Firm	59
Investing Experience		
Group 1	5-10 years	32
Group 2	11-20 years	39
Group 3	>20 years	39

Inferential analysis:

The null hypotheses were set as the sample mean (\bar{x}) equals the hypothesized population mean (μ). Summary of the ratings for the agreement levels are given in Table 2 below:

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Table 2: Effectiveness rating of responses for marketing of financial services

Service	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Average effectiveness rating	3.28	3.21	3.13	3.17	3.30	3.15	3.12	3.18	3.30	3.16	3.20

Table 3 shows the testing of the hypothesis at 95% confidence level.

Table 3: Testing of the hypotheses

Parameter	H1 value
Sample Mean (\bar{x})	3.20
Hypothesized population mean (μ)	3.00
SD of sample	0.9129
N	110
t-value	2.2976
p-value	0.01175
Decision	Reject Null

The null hypothesis was rejected in favour of the alternate that the sample mean is significantly different from the hypothesized population mean.

Discussion of results

All the ten financial services fetched high ratings for their effectiveness of marketing. Services like Banking, Wealth Management, Professional advisory, Mutual Funds, Insurance, Treasury/ Debt instruments, Stock Market, Tax and Audit Consultancy, Portfolio Management, and Funding services were rated above “3” on a the maximum scale of 4. Given the p-value of <0.05, the null hypothesis that the marketing of the financial services is not effectiveness stands rejected.

Conclusion

There was wide agreement that the financial services are marketed quite well. This is an encouraging sign for the Indian capital markets. What is indeed worth noting is that all the ten services have been rated above 3 scale-level on the scale. The marketing efforts need to be appreciated for capturing the length and breadth of the financial services market. At the same time credit should be given to the Government for some of its bold moves like demonetization and investor awareness programs.

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